

Method of Rate Measurement—Stock solutions of phenols (0.005 *M*) and lead tetraacetate (0.01 *M*) both in acetic acid were taken in black bottles and kept in a thermostat in order to attain the temperature of the bath. 25 ml. of the phenol solution were withdrawn and added to 25 ml. of the lead tetraacetate solution. The course of the reaction was followed by withdrawing 5 ml. aliquots of the reaction mixture and estimating the amount of unreacted lead tetraacetate by the method given by Pausacker¹⁰.

The rate constants were calculated by using second order rate equation.

The rate constants together with the parameters of the transition state theory are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

*Values of rate constant and activation parameters for lead tetraacetate oxidation of phenols**

Sl. No.	Name of phenols	$k_{30} \times 10^3$ ¹ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	E in K.cal/mole	ΔF^\ddagger K.cal/mole	ΔS^\ddagger Cal/degree
1	Phenol	115.20	12.90	19.50	-21.9
2	<i>p</i> -Cl	84.45	16.10	19.60	-11.5
3	<i>O</i> -Cl	92.01	15.10	19.60	-14.9
4	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.21	19.80	22.20	- 7.9
5	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1.30	14.40	21.10	- 8.9
6	<i>O</i> -NO ₂	1.24	18.90	21.10	- 7.5

¹The rate of *p*-methyl phenol was very fast. It could not be measured at the experimental conditions.

DISCUSSION

The reaction turns out to be a second order one depending on concentration changes of both reactants and an approximate value of rate constant at 30° of 11.55 l.mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ is obtained.

The order of reactivity of the substituted phenols have been found to conform to the following order (Table 1).

Isokinetic Relationship: A linear relationship between entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) has been found in the present investigation¹¹. The value of ' β ', the isokinetic temperature¹² was computed to be 322°K. This value for ' β ' is unexpectedly low because Exner¹³ has stated that the isokinetic temperature is always far from experimentally accessible temperature. The value of ' β ' calculated by the method

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suggested by Exner was found to be 684°K. Since $T_2/T_1 = 0.99$, these results put the reaction in Exner's category 3(a), namely the most common category¹³. We conclude, therefore, that the reaction of substituted phenols with lead tetraacetate is normal and a linear relationship exists between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger given by

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + 684 \Delta S^\ddagger$$

The value of Hammett reaction constant¹⁴ ' ρ ' was found to be -0.78 . The negative value of ' ρ ' suggests that electron releasing groups enhance the reaction rate and electron attracting groups retard it.

Our results are best explained by a free radical mechanism involving a stepwise progress into the final product as suggested by Waters¹⁵. The initial process is the dehydrogenation¹⁶ of phenol to a phenoxy radical which then rearranges to yield acetoxy dienones and the formation of such products are being assisted by the propagation of acetate radical in acetic acid¹⁷.

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